

Biodiversity documentation of Mulund-Bhandup mangroves and their surroundings: A citizen science approach

Gaurav S. Soman.

Butterflies of Mulund, Mulund (East), Mumbai, Maharashtra, India 400081

Email:gssoman85@gmail.com

Abstract:

The Mulund-Bhandup mangroves include parts of Thane Creek, Bhandup Pumping Station, and the surrounding suburban areas in Mumbai. Despite being on the edge of a metropolis, this area demonstrates an impressive range of flora and fauna. Present study documents the biodiversity in the region using citizen science tools and assesses the possibility of resident individuals contributing meaningfully towards scientific data collection. Through this study, multiple species of plants, birds, and pollinators were recorded and submitted to these open-source platforms. Apart from registering the species data, these observations draw attention to the complex inter-dependencies within the ecosystem. The baseline data collected intends to provide a framework for future studies to monitor the conservation status of this area through community involvement. Lastly, it emphasizes the importance of community awareness and developing future growth opportunities for stakeholders.

Keywords:

Mulund-Bhandup Mangroves, Biodiversity, Citizen Science, iNaturalist, eBird

Introduction:

Mangrove ecosystems are vital for coastal biodiversity, serving as nurseries for numerous species and offering essential ecosystem services such as carbon sequestration. Their intricate root systems provide sustenance for multiple terrestrial and aquatic organisms. Mumbai's mangroves have been extensively documented through various studies and reports, including recent records maintained by the Mangrove Foundation. Insights into Thane Creek's intertidal fauna was provided by Quadros (2001), while Mahul Creek's biodiversity was highlighted by Verma (2004). Significant impacts from sewage discharge and industrial pollutants were revealed by concurrent studies, with traces detected in Thane Creek (Krishnamurti 1999; Athalye 2004; Sasamal 2007). Heavy metal contamination in sediments has exacerbated the degradation of these ecosystems, threatening their health and sustainability (Singare et al. 2013). Documentation of key mangrove species was advanced (Dutta et al. 2019), and extensive studies on avifauna, including the Bhandup Pumping Station, were conducted (Bhagat 2015; Pachpande 2016; Adhikari 2019; Bhave 2022; Lenka 2023; Kasambe 2022). These efforts culminated in the setting-up of Thane Creek Flamingo Sanctuary (Vanita 2021) and its subsequent designation as a potential Ramsar site (Ramsar Sites Information Service, 2022).

Integration of citizen science into biodiversity monitoring has emerged as a pivotal tool in contemporary conservation efforts. Recent accounts highlight the role of citizen science in advancing biodiversity monitoring and conservation (Ceccaroni et al. 2023, Ahern et al. 2024). These reports showcase the transformative impact of public engagement and community-driven initiatives. Engaging volunteers effectively in biodiversity monitoring can

greatly improve conservation outcomes, as demonstrated by (Jansen 2024). The simplicity, cost-effectiveness, and open accessibility of citizen science tools make them particularly valuable for expanding monitoring capabilities. Despite its global growth, especially during the lockdown (Coldren 2022), citizen science remains in its infancy in India, with significant potential for expansion and impact yet to be fully realized. With this promise, the community involvement approach holds promise for enhancing data collection and fostering deeper connections between local stakeholders, especially in the mangrove environment.

Material and methods:

The Mulund-Bhandup mangroves and surrounding accessible area (**Figure 1, Open streetmaps**), located at coordinates 19.1548° N, 72.9692° E, were studied through regular field visits from June 2023 to July 2024. Observations were recorded with naked eyes or binoculars (for birds) along with field notes and photographs. All the observations were uploaded to citizen science portals iNaturalist and eBird with essential details such as GPS location, Photographs and Sound recordings (For birds). Observations were identified using reference material (Books, Field guides etc.) and verified using community observation on eBird and iNaturalist. As part of the current study, only wild observations with Research Grade (RG) observations made during the past year are included.

Figure 1: Mulund-Bhandup mangroves and surroundings: (A) Area under study, (B) Study design

Results:

Mangroves, specialized plants adapted to saline coastal environments, form the backbone of the ecosystem. In the Mulund-Bhandup mangroves, several key mangrove species were documented, including Holly Mangrove (*Acanthus ilicifolius*), Grey Mangrove (*Avicennia marina*), Indian Mangrove (*Avicennia officinalis*), Apple Mangrove (*Sonneratia alba*), and Sonneratia Mangrove (*Sonneratia apetala*). Mangrove-associated species, which benefit from the unique conditions of mangrove ecosystems without being as specialized, were also

identified. These include Rosary Pea (*Abrus precatorius*), Common Derris (*Derris trifoliata*), Velvet Bean (*Mucuna pruriens*), Turpeth (*Operculina turpethum*), Jukti (*Stephanotis volubilis*), Indian Caper (*Capparis sepiaria*), Meswak (*Salvadora persica*), Five-leaved Chaste Tree (*Vitex negundo*), Babul (*Acacia nilotica*), and Portia Tree (*Thespesia populnea*).

Figure 2: Diversity of plants found in the study area

Vegetation Diversity

Vegetation in the surrounding area exhibited significant diversity (**Figure 2**) in terms of habit and growth patterns. A total of 90 plant species were documented (**Supplementary data table 1**) including climbers (15 species), grasses (4 species), herbs (15 species), shrubs (16 species), and trees (40 species). Prevalent climbers included Bush Grape (*Causonis trifolia*) and Ivy Gourd (*Coccinia grandis*). During the monsoon season, grasses such as Panicum, wild rice and millets were prominent, while seasonal flowering plants like Sesame (*Sesamum indicum*), Garden Balsam (*Impatiens balsamina*), Quail Grass (*Celosia argentea*), and Tridax procumbens (*Tridax Daisy*) supported pollinator populations. Herbaceous layer vegetation included ground-dwelling plants like Desmodium, Moneyworts, and Tridax Daisy, providing ground cover. In winter and summer, the landscape shifted to dried grasses, shrubs, and small bushes. Non-marshy areas consisted of dry-deciduous and evergreen trees, with shrubs such as Castor bean, Calotropis, and Caesar Weed, and canopy trees like Indian Beach Tree, Palash, Ficus, and Jungli Badam.

Animal Diversity

The presence of both mangrove and non-mangrove vegetation supports a diverse range of animal life in the Mulund-Bhandup area (**Figure 3**). Insects (69%) and birds (22%) were the most well-represented groups, while mammals (3%), spiders (3%), and a small proportion of molluscs, reptiles, and amphibians were also present. Notably uncommon species such as the

Indian Grey Mongoose (*Urva edwardsii*) and Golden Jackal (*Canis aureus*), were documented in dense forest patches around Bhandup Pumping Station (**Supplementary data table 2**).

Figure 3: Diversity of animals found in the study area

Birds

A total of 23 bird families were recorded in the mangrove habitat (**Figure 4**). The most represented family was Ardeidae with 7 species, followed by Rallidae and Scolopacidae, each with 3 species. Other families, including Anatidae, Laridae, Cisticolidae, and Columbidae, were represented by 2 species each. Remaining families had either 1 or 2 species, reflecting a diverse but uneven distribution of bird families (**Supplementary data table 3**).

Figure 4: Diversity of Birds (No. of species observed per family)

Bird Diet and Habitat Preferences

Bird diets were categorized into six guilds: omnivores, vertebrate and carrion feeders, invertebrate feeders, plant and seed feeders, fruit and nectar feeders, and carnivores (**Figure 5**). Omnivores and vertebrate/carrion feeders each constituted 26% of the observed species, with invertebrate feeders at 24%. Plant and seed feeders made up 15%, and fruit and nectar feeders were the smallest group at 9%.

Figure 5: Dietary preferences of birds

Habitat preferences were divided into five categories: wetland, open habitat, forest and plantation, and non-specialized. Wetland specialists were the most common (24 species), followed by non-specialized species (20 species). Forest and plantation specialists comprised 4 species, open habitat specialists 2 species (**Figure 6**).

Figure 6: Habitat preferences of birds

Insects

Among insects (**Figure 7**), butterflies and moths were the most numerous, indicating their robust presence. Bees and wasps also showed considerable diversity and abundance. Other insect groups, such as grasshoppers, ants, beetles, and bugs, exhibited moderate diversity, while mantids, midges, and lacewings were less prominent (**Supplementary data table 4**).

Figure 7: Diversity of insects (No. of species observed per group)

Diversity indices:

To evaluate the ecological significance of the observed fauna, we calculated diversity indices for birds and pollinators. For birds, the analysis revealed a species richness of 28, with moderate diversity as indicated by the Shannon-Wiener Index (3.17) and Shannon-Weaver Index (2.534), high diversity according to Simpson's Index (0.95), and a high degree of evenness (0.809). In contrast, pollinators showed a species richness of 15, moderate diversity with Shannon-Wiener (2.18) and Shannon-Weaver (2.678) indices, high diversity based on Simpson's Index (0.85), and a very high evenness (0.988). These results suggest that both bird and pollinator communities exhibit substantial diversity, with birds showing a broad range of species and evenness in their distribution, while pollinators demonstrate similar levels of diversity but with even greater evenness.

Discussion:

The Mulund-Bhandup area illustrates the crucial role that mangroves and their associated species play in sustaining the health of coastal environments. Rich diversity of plant species, including a dominance of trees and herbs, is essential for maintaining habitat structure, which supports a variety of animal species (**Figure 8**). Limited presence of grasses, except during the monsoon season, suggests that open grassland areas within the mangrove ecosystem are sparse. Presence of non-mangrove plants reflects on an intricate interrelation between natural and human-influenced elements. Many of these species have been introduced for economic purposes, such as wood, fruit, or medicinal uses, and their proliferation can be attributed to local planting for commercial or personal reasons, as well as afforestation initiatives aimed at

increasing green cover. Urbanization has also facilitated the spread of these non-mangrove species, blending them with natural mangrove vegetation and asserting the impact of ground pollution. Dominance of insects in the animal observations highlights their integral role in the ecosystem. These pollinators interact with the diverse plant life, providing ample food resources and habitat niches. In turn, this invertebrate diversity supports a range of insectivorous birds and mammals, reflecting the interdependent nature of the ecosystem. Birds benefit from available food sources and nesting sites, playing a crucial role in seed dispersal and maintaining plant diversity. Relatively lower numbers of mammals, spiders, and other animal groups may suggest specific habitat preferences, but their presence is crucial for ecological balance, pest control, and nutrient cycling.

Figure 8: Ecological inter-relations found in the Mangroves

Conclusion

The dynamic nature of mangrove ecosystems presents challenges that can offset their ecological potential. Traditional methods like topographical surveys and remote sensing often fail to capture the real-time, fine-scale ecological dynamics of on-the-ground observations. To address these limitations, this survey utilizes citizen science platforms to connect local communities, enabling the collection and validation of species-specific data and enhancing overall understanding. Current assessment of the Mulund-Bhandup mangroves provides a comprehensive overview of the diverse species within this critical coastal ecosystem, emphasizing the complex relationships between plant and animal species that contribute to the area's health and resilience. This documentation highlights the significance of these habitats not only as wildlife refuges but also as vital resources for the surrounding urban environment. This baseline study is a crucial step in understanding the full extent of biodiversity within these mangroves, offering a detailed overview of species distribution that will serve as a reference for monitoring future changes. The involvement of citizen scientists through platforms like iNaturalist and eBird has proven effective, combining scientific rigour with community engagement. Building on this foundation, future studies can refine

methodologies and expand community involvement, contributing to more effective conservation strategies and the long-term preservation of these vital ecosystems.

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